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WOMEN INSURANCE ENTREPRENEUR AS THE WAY FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

Director,
Dr. Dheeraj Negi,
Principapal,
CBM College, Bedia
Distt.- Khargone MP

Researcher,
Smt. Shweta Pancholia,
Ass. Pro.,
Department Manegement,
SRGBN College Sanawad,
Distt.- Khargone MP

ABSTRACT

The role of women entrepreneurs has changed over the years in the world. Participation and their importance have been commendable in the country's economic growth and development. The World Development Report, 2012 represents that women owned businesses show great potential source of future for economic growth and job creation. Therefore, many initiatives have been started by United Nations to promote and motivate women entrepreneurship in developing and under developed countries, such as efforts in Sub- Saharan African countries. Entrepreneurs play a key role in any economy. These are the people who have the skills and initiative necessary to take good new ideas to market and make the right decisions to make the idea profitable. The reward for the risks taken is the potential economic profits the entrepreneur could earn. Technically, a "women entrepreneur" is any women who organizes and manages any enterprise, usually with considerable initiative and risk. However, quite often the term "women-owned business" is used relative to government contracting. In this instance, the entrepreneur (a woman) owns (more than 50%), controls and runs the enterprise. Data has been collected from number of articles, books, periodicals and websites. The present study has been an attempt to generate awareness and to understand meaning, rationale for diversification. An extensive literature review is done on women entrepreneur. At the end some major problems faced by Indian women entrepreneurs, success stories of Indian women entrepreneurs, factors influencing women entrepreneurship and steps taken by the government for upliftment of Indian women entrepreneurs.

Keywords : Meaning of women entrepreneur, rationale for diversification, problems faced by Indian women entrepreneurs, success stories of Indian women entrepreneurs ,factors influencing women entrepreneurship, steps taken by the Indian government.

INTRODUCTION

Women entrepreneurs may be defined as a “Woman or a group of women who initiate, organize and run a business enterprise”. Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs based on women participation in equity and employment of a business enterprise. Accordingly, a woman run a enterprise is defined as “an enterprise owned and controlled by a women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51%of the employment generated in the enterprise to women”. Women entrepreneur constitute 10 % of the number of the number of entrepreneur in the country. This has been a significant growth in self-employment of women with women now starting new ventures at three times the rate of men. They constitute 50% of the population of our country with a lower literacy rate than men. This statistical fact indicates that for the economic growth of the nation, women should not be encouraged to make their share of economic contribution towards the country. one way of achieving is by making women come out and become entrepreneurs. In the traditional society, they were confined to the four walls, playing household roles, but in the modern society, they are coming out to participate in all sorts od activities. Normally, women entrepreneurship is found in the extension of their kitchen activities, mainly in preparing commercially the 3“P”s namely, Pickles, Papads and Powder. Few of them venture into services industry relating to hospitality, catering, educational services, consultation or public relations, beauty clinics, etc. ‘You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women.’ – *Jawaharlal Nehru* Empowerment of women has emerged as an important issue in recent times. The economic empowerment of women is being regarded these days as a Sine-quo-non of progress for a country; hence, the issue of economic empowerment of women is of paramount importance to political thinkers, social scientists and reformers.

The emergence of women entrepreneurs and their contribution to the national economy is quite visible in India. The number of women entrepreneurs has grown over a period of time, especially in the 1990s. Women entrepreneurs need to be lauded for their increased utilisation of modern technology, increased investments, finding a niche in the export market, creating a sizeable employment for others, and setting the trend for other women entrepreneurs in the organised sector. While women entrepreneurs have demonstrated their potential, the fact remains that they are capable of contributing much more than what they already are. Women’s entrepreneurship needs to be studied separately for two main reasons. The first reason is that women entrepreneurship has been recognised during the last decade as an important untapped source of economic growth. Women’s entrepreneurship needs to be studied separately for two main reasons. The first reason is that women’s entrepreneurship has been recognised during the last decade as an important untapped source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others and by

being different also provide society with different solutions to management, organisation and business problems as well as to the exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities. However, they still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Thus there exists a market failure discriminating against women's possibility to become entrepreneurs and their possibility to become successful entrepreneurs. This market failure needs to be addressed by policy makers so that the economic potential of this group can be fully utilised. While without a doubt the economic impact of women is substantial, we still lack a reliable picture describing in detail that specific impact. Recent efforts initiated by the OECD (1997, 2000) are responses to this lack of knowledge and have focused the attention of policy makers and researchers on this important topic.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bowen & Hisrich, (1986), compared & evaluated various research studies done on entrepreneurship including women entrepreneurship. It summaries various studies in this way that female entrepreneurs are relatively well educated in general but perhaps not in management skills, high in internal locus of control, more masculine, or instrumental than other women in their values likely to have had entrepreneurial fathers, relatively likely to have frts born or only children, unlikely to start business in traditionally male dominated industries & experiencing a need of additional managerial training.

Cphoon, Wadhwa & Mitchell, (2010), present a detailed exploration of men & women entrepreneur's motivations, background and experiences. The study is based on the data collected from successful women entrepreneurs. Out of them 59% had founded two or more companies. The study identifies top five financial & psychological factors motivating women to become entrepreneurs. These are desire to build the wealth, the wish to capitalize own business ideas they had, the appeal of startup culture, a long standing desire to own their own company and working with someone else did not appeal them. The challenges are more related with entrepreneurship rather than gender. However, the study concluded with the requirement of further investigation like why women are so much concerned about protecting intellectual capital than their counterpart. Mentoring is very important to women, which provides encouragement & financial support of business partners, experiences & well developed professional network. Women network report on Women in Business & in Decision Making focus on women entrepreneurs, about their problems in starting & running the business, family back ground, education, size of business unit. Some interesting facts which came out from this report are less educated women entrepreneurs are engaged in micro enterprises, have husband & children but have no help at home. Most of the women establish enterprises before the age of 35, after gaining some experience as an employee somewhere else. The

motivational factors were desire for control & freedom to take their own decision as well as earning handsome amount of money. Dedication of more than 48 hours in a week with the family support to their enterprises gave them a sense of self confidence. However, to maintain balance between family & work life is a major challenge before women entrepreneurs especially for those who have children & working husband. Darrene, Harpel and Mayer, (2008) performed a study on finding the relationship between elements of human capital and self employment among women. The study showed that self employed women differ on most human capital variable as compared to the salary and wage earning women. The study also revealed the fact that the education attainment level is faster for self employed women than that for other working women. The percentage of occupancy of managerial job is found to be comparatively higher in case of self employed women as compared to other working women. This study also shed light on similarity and dissimilarity of situations for self employed men and self employed women. Self employed men and women differ little in education, experience and preparedness. However, the main difference lies in occupational and industry experience. The percentage of population holding management occupation is lower for self employed women as compared to self employed men. Also the participation levels of self employed women are found to be less than of self employed men in industries like communication, transportation, wholesale trade, manufacturing and construction. The analysis is based on data from the Current Population Survey (CPS) Annual Social and Economic Supplement (ASEC) from 1994 to 2006. Singh, 2008, identifies the reasons & influencing factors behind entry of women in entrepreneurship. He explained the characteristics of their businesses in Indian context and also obstacles & challenges. He mentioned the obstacles in the growth of women entrepreneurship are mainly lack of interaction with successful entrepreneurs, social un-acceptance as women entrepreneurs, family responsibility, gender discrimination, missing network, low priority given by bankers to provide loan to women entrepreneurs. He suggested the remedial measures like promoting micro enterprises, unlocking institutional frame work, projecting & pulling to grow & support the winners etc. The study advocates for ensuring synergy among women related ministry, economic ministry & social & welfare development ministry of the Government of India. Empirical evidence shows that women contribute significantly to the running of family businesses mostly in the form of unpaid effort and skills. The development of women entrepreneurship has become an important aspect of our plan priorities. Several policies and programmes are being implemented for the development of women entrepreneurship in India (www.indiatogether.org/women/business/renewa_vishwanathan).

The case of Rama Devi, who is currently president of the Association of Lady Entrepreneurs of Andhra Pradesh (ALEAP), portrays that she was pushed into her current business, which was

initially started by her husband and ran into huge losses, although today she can claim to have revived Shivani Engineering Industries (articles.economicstimes.indiatimes.com).

According to Sanjukta Mishra, a study by Dr Joshi, H.G. Ms Veena Rao ICTTM Global Institute of Management, Bhubaneswar-the industrial performance of Asia-Pacific region propelled by Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), technological innovations and manufactured exports has brought a wide range of economic and social opportunities to women entrepreneurs. The development of women entrepreneurship has become an important aspect of our plan priorities.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Women entrepreneurship is growing at a rapid rate in the world. The factors influencing these women across sectors globally are opportunities created by globalisation, integrated markets and jobs, support from the family, major support from the government through various programmes started internationally and domestically for women entrepreneurs, improvement in their standards, and health and education. Table 1 shows the benefits of entrepreneurship and empowerment. This includes rise in income, self worth, self confidence and social status in life. Due to empowerment and motivation, women entrepreneurs create employment for many more women in the community and in a country. Then only a country will be considered inclusive.

PROBLEMS FACED BY INDIAN WOMEN INSURANCE ENTREPRENEURS

Besides the above basic problems the other problems faced by women entrepreneurs are as follows:

1 Family ties:

Women in India are very emotionally attached to their families. They are supposed to attend to all the domestic work, to look after the children and other members of the family. They are over burden with family responsibilities like extra attention to husband, children and in laws which take away a lots of their time and energy. In such situation, it will be very difficult to concentrate and run the enterprise successfully.

2 Male dominated society:

Even though our constitution speaks of equality between sexes, male chauvinism is still the order of the day. Women are not treated equal to men. Their entry to business requires the approval of the head of the family. Entrepreneurship has traditionally been seen as a male preserve. All these puts a break in the growth of women entrepreneurs.

3 Lack of education:

Women in India are lagging far behind in the field of education. Most of the women (around sixty per cent of total women) are illiterate. Those who are educated are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterpart partly due to early marriage, partly due to son's higher education and partly due to poverty. Due to lack of proper education, women entrepreneurs remain in dark about the development of new technology, new methods of production, marketing and other governmental support which will encourage them to flourish.

4 Social barriers:

The traditions and customs prevailed in Indian societies towards women sometimes stand as an obstacle before them to grow and prosper. Castes and religions dominate with one another and hinders women entrepreneurs too. In rural areas, they face more social barriers. They are always seen with suspicious eyes.

5 Shortage of raw materials:

The scarcity of raw materials, sometimes nor, availability of proper and adequate raw materials sounds the death-knell of the enterprises run by women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs really face a tough task in getting the required raw material and other necessary inputs for the enterprises when the prices are very high.

SUCCESSFUL LEADING INSURANCE AND OTHER BUSINESS WOMEN IN INDIA

The 21st leading business women in India:-

- Akhila srinivasan, Managing Director , Shriram Investments Ltd.
- Chanda Kocchar, Executive Director, ICICI Bank
- Ekta Kapoor, Creative Director, balaji Telefilms Ltd.
- Jyoti Naik, President, Lijjat Papad.
- Kiran Mazumdar Shaw, Chairman & Managing director, Biocon Ltd.
- Lalita D.Gupte, JMD , ICICI Bank.
- Naina Lal Kidwar, Deputy CEO, HBSE.
- Preetha Reddy , Managing Director, Apollo hospitals.
- Priya Paul, Chairman, Apeejay Park Hotels.
- Rajshree Pathy, Chairman, Rajshree Sugars & Chemicals ltd.
- Ranjana Kumar, Chairman, NABARD.

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CONCLUSIONS

India is a male dominated society and women are assumed to be economically as well as socially dependent on male members. Women entrepreneurs faced lots of problems like lack of education, social barriers, legal formalities, high cost of production, male dominated society, limited managerial ability, lack of self confidence etc. Various factors like Pull and Push factors influencing women entrepreneurs. Successful leading business women in India. Government takes various steps for the upliftment of women entrepreneurs in 7th five year plan,8th five year plan and in 9th five year plan. Women have the potential the potential and determination to setup, uphold and supervise their own enterprise in a very systematic manner, appropriate support and encouragement from the society, family, government can make these women entrepreneur a part of mainstream of national economy and they can contribute to the economy progress of India. Women entrepreneurship is both about women's position in the society *and* about the role of entrepreneurship in the same society. Women entrepreneurs face many obstacles, specifically in marketing their product (including family responsibilities), that have to be overcome in order to give them access to the same opportunities as men. The entry of rural women in micro- enterprises must be encouraged and aggravated. Rural

women can do wonders by their effectual and competent involvement in entrepreneurial activities. In this study we have assessed the importance of women's entrepreneurship. From an Austrian-economic perspective we have analysed the characteristics of women's entrepreneurship and offered a set of policy recommendations. As we still do not know enough of the entrepreneurial process and women we have argued that better knowledge about the economic importance of women's entrepreneurship and their particular strengths, weaknesses and opportunities, is central. As low rates of women's entrepreneurship are both related to the status of women and the status of entrepreneurship, we have suggested that increasing the abilities of women to participate in the labour force and generally to improve the position of women in society and generally increase the possibility to engage in entrepreneurship is central. However, more targeted initiatives are also needed to support women entrepreneurs and would be entrepreneurs.

REFERENCES

2003. The Prime Minister's Task Force on Women Entrepreneurs Report and Recommendations. Canada: www.liberal.parl.gc.ca/entrepreneur.
- Acs, Z. J. 2002. *Innovations and the Growth of Cities*: Edward Elgar.
- Acs, Z. J., Audretsch, D. B., & Feldman, M. P. 1994. R & D spillovers and recipient firm size. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 76(2): 336-340.

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Bowen, Donald D. & Hirsch Robert D. (1986), The Female Entrepreneur: A career Development Perspective, Academy of Management Review, Vol. 11 no. 2, Page No. 393-407.

Cohoon, J. McGrath, Wadhwa, Vivek & Mitchell Lesa, (2010), The Anatomy of an Entrepreneur- Are Successful Women Entrepreneurs Different From Men? Kauffman, The foundation of entrepreneurship.

Women Entrepreneurship Development in India,

www.indianmba.com/Faculty_Column/FC1073/fc1073.html

<http://www.entrepreneur.com/article/227163>

<http://www.indiatvnews.com/business/india/breaking-news-successful-femaleentrepreneurs-india-3242.html?page=7>

<http://www.dcmsme.gov.in/schemes/treadwomen.htm>

<http://www.dcmsme.gov.in/data-stat.htm>